

MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGE

Bahromova O'g'iloy

Fergana State University, Faculty of English Language and Literature, 2nd year

Annotation: The topic of the paper is how to use cutting-edge pedagogical innovations to teach foreign languages effectively.

Keywords: Communicative competence, the formation of professional competencies, education, students, English.

Аннотация: Тема статьи – как использовать передовые педагогические инновации для эффективного обучения иностранным языкам.

Ключевые слова: Коммуникативная компетентность, формирование профессиональных компетенций, образование, студенты, английский.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada zamonaviy innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalardan foydalangan holda xorijiy tillarni o'qitishda qanday qilib yuqori natijalarga erishish mumkinligi haqida so'z boradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Kommunikativ kompetensiya, kasbiy kompetensiyalarni shakllantirish, ta'lim, talabalar, ingliz tili.

Like any other language, learning a foreign language is largely for communication. Therefore, the objective of teaching a foreign language today is for pupils to master conversational abilities. According to our perspective, such techniques as mindless memorization of foreign language texts have no place at a modern institution. These techniques offer the young specialists no useful benefits for their future. In later life and at employment, students must be able to utilize the language intentionally.

Modern employers value candidates with strong language skills. The two main methods that methodological science separates are communicative and constructivist. The capacity to recognize different speech patterns that enable you to construct behavioural tactics and background settings in the course of professional communication is known as discursive competence.

Formation In the context of professional work, lexical competence enables you to create a meaningful vocabulary and fill it with varied terms. Our opinion is that thematic texts combine intensive and thorough reading promotion based on training session experience and students' passive knowledge while also taking into account the priority learning and extracurricular activities. Need Text must use a range of dictionaries and should increase student vocabulary as needed. The interaction between

text and verbal context enables you to broaden the lexical scope, streamline word usage, and create thematic texts that blend lexical and semantic types.

Language proficiency is the development of knowledge of language concepts (phonetics, vocabulary, grammar), as well as proficiency in a variety of speech activities (listening, speaking, reading and writing). According to a particular speaking context, communication aim, and desire, sociolinguistic competency enables the speaker to select an appropriate language form and expression style.

The ability to understand the national characteristics of authentic speech, including customs, values, rituals, and other national and cultural features of the country in which they live and compare them with the country where the language is being studied, is a component of sociolinguistic competence.

Communication strategy. The mastery of communication skills is its aim. This method's exercises are usually communicative in nature. Orientation. Through their interactions with one another, students develop their communication skills.

Consequently, professional competency development is a process that is not just a part of education. Increased subjectivity and motivation among students to learn English enables them to begin the process of developing their professional competencies over time.

REFERENCES:

1. Расходова И. А, Еремина А. С, Россия, г. Казань 2020 страница 396
2. Валеева Р. Р., Гисматуллина А. И. Технология коллективного обучения. Международная научно-практическая конференция „Целевая подготовка Кадров: направления, технологии и эффективность“. Казань, 2019. — С. 42–44.
3. Волкова Н. П. Педагогика: учеб, пособие. — Киев: Академвидав, 2007.
4. Кузьминский А. И., Омельяненко В. Л. Педагогика: учебник. — М.: ЗнаниеПресс, 2008.

